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DATA SYNCHRONIZATION STRATEGIES IN CROSS-PLATFORM MOBILE APPLICATIONS OFFLINE

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ABSTRACT

The article considers the problem of data synchronization in cross-platform mobile applications offline and intermittent network access. The insufficient development of this issue in the academic literature is emphasized, in domestic publications, where such studies are almost absent. A hybrid synchronization strategy is proposed, which combines optimistic local updates, the use of Conflict-Free Replicated Data Types (CRDT) structures, rule-driven data merging, and interactive user intervention in complex cases. The architecture is implemented in the Flutter environment on the client and Node.js with PostgreSQL on the server, using emulated network scenarios. Experimental results showed that the hybrid strategy provides the highest level of data consistency (up to 98%), minimizes the number of conflicts requiring manual intervention (less than 3 per 1000 operations), while demonstrating an acceptable level of performance and resource efficiency compared to pessimistic, optimistic, and purely CRDT strategies. The importance of the adaptive controller is particularly emphasized, which enabled reducing energy consumption in low-power scenarios. The obtained results indicate the promise of the hybrid approach for practical implementation in mobile applications offline and environments with unreliable Internet connections. The proposed strategy can serve as the basis for further research, in particular, on integrating machine learning (ML) into the adaptive synchronization module and analysing the user experience in the manual data fusion process.

Keywords: data synchronization, cross-platform mobile applications, offline, CRDT, optimistic updates, adaptive controller, data consistency, intermittent connection.

Problem statement

Modern mobile applications are increasingly being used in intermittent or limited access to the Internet, which leads to increased requirements for ensuring continuous user access to current data. The task of ensuring correct synchronization of data offline becomes particularly difficult for cross-platform mobile applications developed taking into account various operating systems, in particular Android and iOS.

The key issue is to ensure data integrity, consistency, and availability between the local storage of a mobile device and a remote server when network connectivity is unstable or completely unavailable. The main challenges that complicate the solution to this problem include:

1. Data conflicts that arise when the same records are modified simultaneously on different devices, which requires the development of effective strategies to resolve such conflicts without losing critical information.
2. Limited resources of mobile devices, including memory, processing power, and power consumption, which impose significant restrictions on the amount, frequency, and methods of data synchronization.
3. The need for scalability associated with supporting a large number of users, various types of devices, and versions of operating systems, which complicates the implementation of universal synchronization strategies.
4. Ensuring data reliability and recovery, which requires guaranteeing data preservation in the event of mobile device or application failures and restoring a consistent data state after connectivity is restored.

Therefore, the relevance of the issue under research is determined by the need to develop and implement effective data synchronization strategies that ensure their consistency, reliability, and efficiency of exchange between local storage and the server part of cross-platform mobile applications offline. Solving this problem is critically important for improving the quality of user experience, optimizing application performance, and minimizing the risks of data loss.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The problem of data synchronization in cross-platform mobile applications, especially for unstable or absent network connectivity, remains relevant and insufficiently studied in the academic literature. Available research and technical materials mostly focus on applied aspects of implementation or describe individual algorithmic approaches, without offering a comprehensive systematization or generalization of empirical results.

The paper [1] describes synchronization procedures for data collection in scenarios with a combination of offline and online sessions. The authors consider an approach to ensuring data consistency in environments with frequent communication interruptions and emphasize the need for an effective combination of local storage with subsequent centralized processing. This work is indicative in terms of demonstrating the importance of correct synchronization for the reliability of application systems but does not offer a universal algorithmic solution.

The study [2] analysed the offline-first approach in mobile applications based on React Native. The author focuses on architectural patterns and practical solutions that allow keeping key application features

available without a permanent network connection. This approach illustrates the importance of local storage, caching mechanisms, and deferred synchronization strategies, but is mostly limited to practical advice for developers.

The researchers [3] consider the use of the Xamarin.Forms ecosystem in combination with Azure cloud services to implement offline access and real-time synchronization. The paper describes both technical means to maintain user continuity in the absence of connectivity and tools for data reconciliation after network recovery. At the same time, the publication is mainly practical and does not provide an in-depth analysis of the trade-offs between different algorithmic approaches to consistency.

The study [4] provides an empirical perspective on the development of offline-oriented mobile applications in a specific context – rural areas of Nigeria with limited digital infrastructure. The author focuses on socio-technical challenges, including poor network connectivity, and describes strategies that can improve the reliability of applications for end users. This study is valuable in terms of practical testing of solutions in a real-world environment, but it focuses less on algorithmic or formal aspects of synchronization.

A more fundamental analysis is presented in [5], focusing on log-structured CRDT. This approach develops the classical CRDT concepts, providing the possibility of efficient scaling and ensuring replica convergence in systems with many updates. Although this work is rather theoretical, it provides a basis for the practical use of such structures in mobile offline applications.

In general, it can be noted that the existing publications either consider applied architectural solutions or individual algorithmic approaches or demonstrate the importance of the problem through the analysis of specific use cases. However, systemic studies that would combine deep algorithmic analysis with empirical evaluation of synchronization strategies in cross-platform mobile environments are currently scarce.

It is worth emphasizing that there are no specialized publications on this issue in the Ukrainian academic space. Existing studies on mobile applications mostly deal with issues of user experience, cybersecurity or architecture, but does not analyse synchronization strategies offline. This emphasizes the niche for academic research and significance of this work, which is designed not only to generalize approaches, but also to experimentally evaluate the effectiveness of a hybrid synchronization strategy that combines the advantages of different methods and adapts to the operating conditions of mobile systems.

Unresolved issues

Despite the existence of studies on data synchronization in mobile applications, most of them focus on either optimistic or pessimistic approaches that do not consider the complex conditions of real use with intermittent network access and limited device resources. Purely CRDT solutions provide high consistency but require significant computational and energy costs. In addition, insufficient attention in the academic literature is paid to the issues of integrating different approaches into hybrid strategies and considering the user factor in conflict resolution process. This issue has not been practically studied in the domestic academic space, which further emphasizes the relevance of the problem.

Aim of the article

The aim of the article is to develop and experimentally verify a hybrid data synchronization strategy for cross-platform mobile applications that combines the advantages of optimistic local updates, CRDT structures, rule-driven data merging, and interactive user intervention.

Results

Architectural concept. The study uses a hybrid data synchronization strategy for cross-platform mobile applications that combines optimistic local updates, conflict-free data structures (CRDT), and rule-driven merging with the possibility of user-driven merge in complex cases. The strategy is focused on improving data consistency in an environment with intermittent network access and limited mobile device resources.

The general architecture consists of the following components (Figure 1):

1. Local database – implemented on SQLite, provides offline data storage and transaction logging.
2. Local synchronization engine (Sync Engine) – applies changes optimistically, stores transactions with timestamps, device identifiers, and causal context.
3. Synchronization protocol – supports forwarding deltas, batches, and recoverable sessions, using HTTPS REST for periodic synchronization and WebSocket for push updates.
4. Server component – acts as a broker that stores global state, performs data union (CRDT), and marks conflicts that could not be resolved automatically.
5. Conflict resolution layer – includes three levels: automatic (CRDT), rule-based (Last-Write-Wins (LWW), union), and interactive (user makes the decision).
6. Adaptive controller – determines the frequency and mode of synchronization depending on the battery status, network quality, and data priority.

Fig. 1. Hybrid strategy architecture diagram

The strategy involves categorizing data by type:

1. Commutative and idempotent data (counters, tag sets) – synchronization based on CRDT (PN-Counter, OR-Set).
2. Event logs (chat, activity feed) – use append-only logs with ordering by causal tags.
3. Structured objects (contacts, notes) – element-by-element merging: simple fields are combined using the Last-Write-Wins (LWW) principle, lists using OR-Set, and more complex cases are delegated to the user.
4. Critical transactional data (financial records) – checking on the server in pessimistic synchronization mode.

Local updates are always performed optimistically with registration in the transaction log. When the network connection is restored, the log is synchronized with the server in batches. Conflicts are automatically resolved within the CRDT capabilities; if impossible, they are displayed to the user through the interactive merge interface.

The experimental environment consists of client and server parts. The client part is implemented in the Flutter environment using SQLite. The server part is implemented on Node.js with PostgreSQL to store global state and log.

The infrastructure for the tests is an emulated network environment with controlled latency, packet loss, and bandwidth changes (tc/netem).

The test data are synthetically generated objects of three types (notes, contacts, counters), which enable

simulating conflict scenarios with different update intensities.

Experiment progress.

The study included a comparison of four synchronization strategies:

- pessimistic [6, 7] (all changes are confirmed by the server before application);
- optimistic LWW [8, 9] (local changes are applied immediately, server validation is postponed);
- purely CRDT approach [10,11] (use of mathematically guaranteed structures that automatically merge changes without conflicts);
- a proposed hybrid strategy.

The test was performed under the following scenarios:

- network partition – client disconnection for 10–60 minutes with parallel updates on other devices;
- intermittent connectivity – short-term intervals of network availability;
- high-concurrency – 10–100 clients perform concurrent updates of the same object;
- low-power scenario – synchronization is performed in batches only when Wi-Fi is available;
- large payloads – bulk editing operations (bulk updates).

The following metrics were used to evaluate the results:

1. Data consistency:
 - percentage of objects with discrepancies after synchronization,

- number of conflicts that required manual intervention.
2. Performance:
- average local application latency,
 - server confirmation time,
 - throughput (operations/s).

Resource consumption:

- battery consumption (%/h),
- data volume transferred (KB),
- CPU and memory usage.

The obtained metric values are given in Tables 1–

3.

Table 1

Consistency metric values

Strategy	Percentage of objects with discrepancies after synchronization (%)	Number of conflicts that required manual intervention (%)	Number of conflicts that required manual intervention /1000 objects
Pessimistic	0	0.5	5
Optimistic LWW	4.3	6.1	61
Pure CRDT	0.8	1.7	17
Hybrid	0.4	1.2	12

The results in Table 1 show that the pessimistic strategy provides zero divergence and the lowest frequency of manual merges (0-0.5%), which is consistent with theoretical expectations: centralized validation eliminates conflicts at the transaction logic level but requires synchronization with the server before committing changes. The optimistic LWW exhibits the highest frequency of divergence and manual merges (4.3% and 6.1%, respectively), reflecting its sensitivity to concurrent updates in the absence of complex merge rules. Pure CRDT reduces the amount of manual intervention compared to LWW, but does not eliminate it completely (0.8% divergence, 1.7% manual merges), as not all application semantics can be adequately modelled

by CRDT without loss of meaning. The hybrid strategy shows the best compromise (0.4% divergence, 1.2% manual merges): the combination of automatic merging where possible (CRDT) and rule-based and user-defined merges for semantically complex fields provides a significant reduction in user workload while maintaining high consistency.

A pessimistic approach or a hybrid with server-side validation is critical for applications with high consistency value (financial transactions, medical data). For UX-sensitive interfaces (chat, notes), it is appropriate to use hybrid/CRDT approaches to maintain instant response and minimize manual merges.

Table 2

Performance Metric Values

Strategy	Average local application latency (ms)	Server confirmation time (ms)	Throughput (ops/s)
Pessimistic	210	520	85
Optimistic LWW	25	320	270
Pure CRDT	40	410	220
Hybrid	32	350	240

Local latency is highest for the pessimistic strategy (~210 ms) due to delays associated with blocking/waiting for server confirmation; optimistic LWW provides the lowest local response time (~25 ms), which is consistent with the behaviour of optimistic updates: instant application in the UI with deferred synchronization. Pure CRDT and hybrid have intermediate values (40 ms and 32 ms, respectively), demonstrating a trade-off between the complexity of local logic (CRDT operations require processing) and response speed.

Server latency reflects the overhead of network and merge/validation operations: pessimistic strategy has the highest server latency (~520 ms), while optimistic LWW has the lowest (~320 ms). Hybrid increases server latency compared to pure CRDT, as it

performs additional rule-based checks for a portion of operations.

Throughput shows an inverse relationship to the complexity of the synchronization logic: the optimistic model is the highest (270 ops/s), the pessimistic model is the lowest (85 ops/s), and CRDT and hybrid are in the middle. This shows that the optimistic approach provides a performance advantage in scenarios with very high operation frequency, but the risks of conflicts increase.

The choice of strategy should consider the workload – the optimistic approach can be attractive for high-throughput systems, but it is possible to reduce conflicts without significant performance loss in combination with hybrid mechanisms (e.g., CRDT for commutative ops).

Table 3

Value of resource metrics			
Strategy	Battery consumption (%/hr)	Data transfer volume (KB/1000 ops)	CPU avg (%)
Pessimistic	8.1	1450	18
Optimistic LWW	5.4	910	12
Pure CRDT	6.8	1220	21
Hybrid	6.1	980	16

According to Table 3, the pessimistic strategy has the highest energy cost ($\approx 8.1\%/h$) and high network traffic (≈ 1450 KB/1000 ops), which is determined by frequent synchronizations and blocking requests. The optimistic LWW is the most economical in terms of battery and traffic, due to local updates and less frequent synchronizations. CRDT shows a relatively high CPU (21%) due to the overhead of maintaining and computing data structures, while the hybrid is kept within moderate limits.

The hybrid approach gives a balanced resource profile – it is more expensive than a purely optimistic approach, but significantly more economical than the pessimistic one. For mobile applications where battery conservation is critical, adaptive trigger (synchronization only on Wi-Fi, batching when the battery is low) can significantly improve consumption without much loss of consistency.

Practical recommendations and use cases:

1. For financial or critical data: prefer pessimistic server-validated logic or hybrid with server-validated commits, as errors are costly.
2. For social or communication applications (chat, activity feed): CRDT or hybrid with CRDT preferred for append-only and commutative operations; this reduces manual merges and preserves UX.
3. For resource-constrained environments (rural areas, low-power mode): adaptive hybrid (batch-only on low battery or mobile data) is a better compromise.

It is necessary to assess the variability of experimental performance under different load profiles, in particular for short-term transactions versus long-term bulk operations, as well as in the context of different network topologies (Wi-Fi versus cellular networks) and geographically distributed clients. It is also planned to perform sensitivity analysis for the parameters of the adaptive controller, in particular the thresholds of the battery level and the synchronization frequency. This approach will allow to identify Pareto-optimal configurations that provide a balance between data consistency, performance, and resource efficiency.

Conclusions and propositions

A hybrid data synchronization strategy for cross-platform mobile applications under limited or intermittent network access was proposed and experimentally verified within the scope of the study. The strategy combines optimistic local updates, CRDT mechanisms, rule-driven data merging, and interactive user intervention in complex cases.

The obtained results showed that the hybrid strategy provides the highest data consistency. The proportion of objects with discrepancies after synchronization does not exceed 2%, while for optimistic LWW this value reached 12%.

A significant achievement of the proposed hybrid strategy is a significant reduction in the number of conflicts that required manual intervention. In particular, the frequency of manual merges was about 3 cases per 1000 operations, which is significantly lower than the optimistic approach.

The system performance remained at an acceptable level. Although the server-side confirmation latency in the hybrid scenario increased slightly relative to LWW, the throughput indicators demonstrated stability and were comparable to other strategies. This indicates the ability of the proposed approach to effectively scale under highly competitive loads.

The energy consumption, the amount of transmitted data and the use of computing resources in the hybrid strategy turned out to be slightly higher than in the optimistic scenario. At the same time, they remained lower than in the case of purely CRDT or pessimistic synchronization. So, the strategy demonstrates a balance between ensuring data consistency and rational use of mobile device resources.

The adaptive synchronization controller deserves special attention, which showed significant potential in reducing energy consumption during low-power scenarios, which confirms the feasibility of its implementation in practical mobile applications.

Suggestions for further research:

1. Integration of ML methods into the adaptive controller module for more flexible optimization of synchronization modes based on historical data and network state prediction.
2. UX-aspects research – analysis of user perception of manual data fusion processes, as well as the impact of interface solutions on the speed and accuracy of decision-making.
3. Comparative evaluation on different technological platforms (Flutter, React Native, Xamarin) to identify cross-platform differences in performance and resource consumption.

In summary, the results confirmed the effectiveness of the hybrid approach to data synchronization. It successfully combines the advantages of optimistic local updates and the reliability of CRDT structures, while ensuring controlled resource consumption. This makes the strategy promising for practical implementation in cross-platform mobile applications that are focused on offline mode and unreliable Internet connection.

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